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An integrated environment friendly approach for recovery of surfactant and potable water from domestic washing machine discharge

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Introduction: It is a well-known fact that the demand of water increases with population increase. W.H.O. reported that by 2025, half of the population will be not able to have a clean source of water (1). Thus, water has to be used judiciously and should not be wasted. Estimates vary, but a typical household use about 80-100 gallons of water per day. The largest use of water in every house is for washing clothes, bathing, toilet flush, washing dishes. Urban waste water which includes water from bath, shower, hand basins, washing machine, dishwashers and kitchen sinks, but excludes streams from toilets is called grey water (2). Grey water which is also primarily discharged from washed laundry contains high in surfactants and is also very high in suspended solids, turbidity and oxygen demand. When the grey water is released without treatment it can cause environmental pollution and serious threat to living being. Currently treatment of laundry water is a challenge because of rapid population growth and also it is not accompanied by infrastructure improvements, especially in the field of sanitation. It is important that wastewater should be treated in order to save water as a future source and protect the environment from pollution. Previously grey water treatment was done physically where pollutants from grey water were removed by coarse sand and soil filtration (3). Now with the advancement of membrane-based water treatment technologies, such treatment methods have come into focus (4). The main object of this study to recover the valuable surfactant solution and generate potable water both of which could be reused again thereby leading to a cost effective, sustainable and environment friendly process.

Methods: An experimental setup has been developed which uses a spiral wound UF membrane that essentially removes the suspended matter from the grey water that was taken as the feed solution. The reject from this membrane is recycled back to the feed tank whereas the permeate enters a spiral wound RO membrane where the surfactant is removed from the solution thereby allowing potable water pass as a permeate. Both the membrane modules were optimized for its operating pressure and flowrates.

Results & Discussions: The collected grey water used for the experiment was found to have TDS of 749 ppm, Turbidity of 106 NTU and BOD of 290 mg/l. On treating it using the UF membranes, the recovered surfactant was found to have a TDS of 830 ppm, turbidity of 12.6 NTU and BOD of 110 mg/l indicating the collection of concentrated surfactant solution. The potable water which was collected later as RO permeate tested to have a TDS of 25 ppm, turbidity of 0.41 NTU and BOD of just 20mg/l indicating that the RO permeate is now potable.

Conclusions: The process leads to an effective separation process where the grey water obtained from washing machine was first cleaned of dirt materials using UF membranes and further separating the surfactant solution from the mixture and yielding potable water. The recovered concentrated surfactant solution as well as potable water could be reused again for future washes. The process thus leads to conservation of water too in addition to being cost effective and environment friendly.

Keywords: Grey water treatment; surfactant recovery; potable water recovery; UF and RO membranes.

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